

Improvement of equipment for studying fluid flow regime using the Reynolds Method

Caiane Oliveira, Guilherme Barbosa, Luan Lima, Mateus Borges, Sidney Soares, Vitor, Araújo, L.M.P, Araújo Filho, W.D.
Scientific Initiation – Jorge Amado University Center Av. Luís Viana Filho, 6775 – Trobogy, Salvador, Bahia Class – Engineering

Abstract: The Reynolds equipment was adjusted to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the experimental system. The process began with the complete disassembly of the equipment, followed by cleaning and removing rust from the table. After cleaning, the equipment was reassembled, focusing on the reconfiguration of the main components. As a final part of the adjustment, a modification was made to the main water outlet, connecting the overflow of the test tank to the water outlet system after the conclusion of the experiment. This provided optimization of the water flow, preventing accumulation or waste and ensuring that the experimental conditions were maintained constant during the tests, a fundamental condition for obtaining reliable results in the study of fluid flows.

Key words: Reynolds, fluid flow, Reynolds method

INTRODUCTION

Reynolds equipment is widely used to study the behaviour of fluid flows, enabling the analysis of different flow regimes, such as laminar, transitional and turbulent. It functions as a teaching and experimental tool to observe how the fluid behaves inside a tube, with the Reynolds number, a dimensionless quantity, being the key parameter for classifying these different types of flow[1]. This number depends on factors such as fluid viscosity, flow velocity, tube diameter and fluid density, playing a crucial role in understanding flow dynamics. The equipment is essential in both educational contexts and scientific investigations, providing important data to validate theories about fluid behaviour. Ensuring the proper and accurate functioning of the system is essential, since appropriate adjustments to the components are necessary to ensure the reliability of the results and the reproducibility of the experiments [4]. To this end, modifications were made to the equipment in order to meet experimental expectations.

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THEORETICAL BASIS

The theoretical basis of fluid flow using the Reynolds method involves concepts related to fluid dynamics, especially regarding the transition between laminar and turbulent flow regimes. This approach is based on the analysis of the Navier-Stokes Equation and the development of experimental and theoretical methods to characterize fluid behaviour [2],[3].

Introduction to Fluid Flow

Fluid flow can be classified into two main regimes:

- Laminar: Organized flow, in which the fluid particles follow parallel trajectories.
- Turbulent: Disordered flow, characterized by chaotic fluctuations in velocity and pressure.

This distinction is made using the Reynolds number (Re), a dimensionless parameter introduced by Osborne Reynolds in 1883. It relates the inertial and viscous forces in the fluid and is calculated by the Equation 1

$$Re = \frac{\rho \cdot v \cdot L}{\mu} = \frac{v \cdot L}{\nu} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- ρ : Density of the fluid [kg/m³]
- v : Characteristic velocity of the fluid [m/s]
- L : Characteristic dimension (such as hydraulic diameter in pipes) [m];
- μ : Dynamic viscosity [Pa·s]
- ν : Kinematic viscosity [m²/s]

Reynolds method

Reynolds Experiment

Reynolds conducted experiments in cylindrical tubes to observe fluid flow patterns. He injected ink into moving water and observed how the ink line behaved:

- At low values of Re , the streamline remains straight (laminar flow).
- At high values of Re , the streamline mixes with the fluid (turbulent flow).

These experiments defined practical limits:

- Laminar Flow: $Re < 2000$
- Transition Region: $2000 < Re < 4000$
- Turbulent Flow: $Re > 4000$

Reynolds approximations

To simplify the study of turbulent flow, Reynolds developed the concept of Reynolds averaging [5]. In this method, the fluid properties (velocity, pressure, etc.) are decomposed into an average part and a fluctuation, Equation 2:

$$u(x, t) = \bar{u}(x) + u'(x, t) \quad (2)$$

Where:

- \bar{u} : Average component (time or space).
- $u'(x, t)$: Fluctuating component.

Substituting this decomposition into the Navier-Stokes equation and applying the time average, we obtain the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) Equations, which describe the average behaviour of the flow.

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations

The resulting average equations are, equation 3:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial \overline{u'_i u'_j}}{\partial x_j} \quad (3)$$

The additional term $(\overline{u'_i u'_j})$ known as the Reynolds stress, represents the effects of turbulent fluctuations, which need to be modeled (as in the k- ϵ model) to close the equations.

O termo adicional $\overline{u'_i u'_j}$ conhecido como **tensão de Reynolds**, representa os efeitos das flutuações turbulentas, que precisam ser modelados (como no modelo k- ϵ) para fechar as equações.

Applications and Importance

The Reynolds method and the Reynolds number have practical applications in several areas of engineering and science, such as:

- Design of pipes and channels.
- Aerodynamics (analysis of flow around wings and fuselages).
- Hydrodynamics (flow of liquids in reservoirs or rivers).
- Prediction of regime transitions in industrial processes.

These analyses allow the optimization of fluid systems, predicting losses due to friction, turbulence and promoting greater efficiency in equipment such as pumps, heat exchangers and turbines [6],[7]. The Reynolds method revolutionized the study of fluids, allowing the characterization and prediction of behaviour in different regimes. The introduction of the Reynolds number and the RANS equations form the basis for the study of laminar and turbulent flows, being indispensable tools in modern engineering.

PROCEDURES AND METHODS

Reynolds' equipment, used in the Hydraulics Laboratory of the Jorge Amado University Center, was out of operation and needed repairs to be able to function again. This equipment is essential for studying different fluid flow regimes, such as laminar, turbulent and transitional flow, and consists of several components, including test tubes, water supply, water and dye tanks, as well as supports and other accessories. In order to restore the equipment to operation, a series of steps were taken. The process began with the complete disassembly of the system, which involved removing the pipes, water and dye tanks, pipe supports and the support box (blue box), along with the rubber mat, leaving only the metal bench. During this phase, the structure was also cleaned, removing rust from the table to ensure a surface suitable for the equipment to operate.

In addition, for safety reasons and to ensure the integrity of the system, almost all welded connections were replaced. Some modifications to the arrangement of the supports were also necessary, adjusting the structure to ensure greater stability. A significant change was also made to the water outlet line, due to the drying out of the existing hose, which was replaced to ensure efficient drainage.

Another important change was made to the system assembly to enable better handling and operation of the tanks. Two handgrips were installed to provide greater stability and ease of manoeuvring, and the dye tank was moved approximately 20 cm forward. In addition, a section of pipe corresponding to this measurement was added to the water outlet of the main tank, next to the nozzle, ensuring that the interconnection between the dye tank and the water tank outlet pipe remained the same as the original arrangement. In the final assembly phase, an adjustment was made to the main water outlet, connecting the overflow of the main test tank to the outlet of the water coming from the end of the experiment. This adjustment aims to optimize the water flow, avoiding waste and ensuring that the experimental conditions remain stable, which is essential for obtaining accurate results during the tests. Figures 1 to 7 represent the stages of the experimental apparatus improvement process.

Imagem 1. Fonte: Autoral.

Figure1. Equipment before disassembly

Figure2. Disassembled equipment

Figure3. Water tank leak test

Figure 4. Saída de água onde foi alterado o arranjo devido ao ressecamento da mangueira existente:

Figure 5. Changing the position of the dye tank:

Figure 6. Pipe Assembly:

Figure7. Equipment completed with the modifications indicated.

CONCLUSION

The restoration of Reynolds' equipment, used in the Hydraulics Laboratory of the Jorge Amado University Center, was an essential process to ensure the continuity of studies on the different fluid flow regimes. After careful repair and adjustment work, the equipment was reconnected and adapted to better meet operational needs, with a focus on safety and efficiency. Disassembly and cleaning of the structure were important steps, as were the replacement of welded connections and the improvement of the stability of the assembly, which increased the durability and functionality of the system. In addition, the modifications made, such as the repositioning of the tanks and the replacement of damaged components, ensured safer and more practical operation. Adjusting the system's water outlet was also a crucial step to optimize the flow and minimize waste, ensuring the accuracy of the experiments. With these repairs, the equipment is in ideal conditions for the study and analysis of laminar, turbulent and transition flows, which are fundamental for the advancement of research in fluid dynamics and hydraulics.

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